

A Mesoscale Model of Woven Fabric Thermoplastic Composites for Large Deformation

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Outline

- ▶ **Motivation**
- ▶ **Experimental campaign**
- ▶ **Mesoscale modeling**
- ▶ **Results and discussion**
- ▶ **Conclusions**

1. Motivation

Carbon fiber woven thermoplastic composites

- High specific strength
- Excellent formability
- Sustainability

Fabric reinforcement

In-plane shear deformation

Yarn reorientation

Non-orthogonal fabric

↓ Draping

Complex geometries

Helmet shell

Pressure vessel

Various degrees of yarn reorientation [1]

Spatially dependent mechanical behavior

[1] M.-G. Han et al., Composites Part A 110 (2018) 172–182.

1. Motivation

Finite element analysis (FEA)

Objective:

- Local mechanical behaviors of woven thermoplastic composites with complex geometries
- A mesoscale RVE damage model accounting for large deformation

2. Experimental campaign

Angle definition

Fabric angle: 60°
Yarn angle: 30°

Fabric angle: 75°
Yarn angle: 37.5°

Fabric angle: 90°
Yarn angle: 45°

Fabric angle: 75°
Yarn angle: 52.5°

Fabric angle: 60°
Yarn angle: 60°

Shear forming of dry fabric

Pull direction

Specimen thermoforming

Stacking sequence

Polycarbonate (PC)

Carbon fabric

Temperature and pressure cycles

2. Experimental campaign

Off-axis uniaxial tests

- Sandpaper tab
- Coupon
- Extensometer
- Strain gauge

ASTM D3039

Digital image correlation (DIC) method

Artificial speckles

3. Mesoscale modeling

Morphologies of coupons

Yarn: transversely isotropic UD composite

- Size parameters
- Fiber volume fractions

Woven composite RVEs

3. Mesoscale modeling

a. Material model-PC matrix

ASTM D638-14

Elasto-plastic parameters

b. Material model-Yarn

Chamis' micromechanical model

Elastic constants

Properties	Carbon fiber []	PC matrix	Fiber yarn
E_{11} (GPa)	230		150.773
$E_{22} = E_{33}$ (GPa)	15	2.466	7.579
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.20		0.259
ν_{23}	0.07	0.37	0.299
$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	27		4.095
G_{23} (GPa)	7	0.899	3.034

Strength parameters

Carbon fiber			PC matrix		
X_{ft} (MPa)	X_{fc} (MPa)	S_{mt} (MPa)	S_{mc} (MPa)	S_{ms} (MPa)	
3530	2470	65.04	80	40	
Fiber yarn					
X_T (MPa)	X_C (MPa)	$Y_T = Z_T$ (MPa)	$Y_C = Z_C$ (MPa)	$S_{12} = S_{13}$ (MPa)	S_{23} (MPa)
2314.03	1619.17	56.59	69.61	33.56	27.45

3. Mesoscale modeling

a. Damage criterion-PC matrix pocket

Abaqus built-in **Ductile failure criterion** with **exponential damage evolution laws**

Facture strain: 0.6021

Fracture energy: 2.18 KJ/m²

b. Damage criterion-Yarn

Strain-based 3D Hashin failure criterion

Failure strains

$$\epsilon_{XT}^f = \frac{X_T}{C_{11}} \quad \epsilon_{XC}^f = \frac{X_C}{C_{11}} \quad \epsilon_{YT}^f = \frac{Y_T}{C_{22}} \quad \epsilon_{YC}^f = \frac{Y_C}{C_{22}} \quad \epsilon_{S12}^f = \epsilon_{S13}^f = \frac{S_{12}}{C_{44}} \quad \epsilon_{S23}^f = \frac{S_{23}}{C_{66}}$$

Tensile failure in the longitudinal (fiber) direction ($\epsilon_{11} \geq 0$)

$$F_{ft} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{XT}^f}\right)^2 + \alpha \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}}{\epsilon_{S12}^f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{13}}{\epsilon_{S13}^f}\right)^2 \right]} > 1$$

Compressive failure in the longitudinal (fiber) direction ($\epsilon_{11} < 0$)

$$F_{fc} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{XC}^f}\right)^2} > 1$$

Tensile failure in the transverse (matrix) direction ($\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} \geq 0$)

$$F_{mt} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33}}{\epsilon_{YT}^f}\right) + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33}}{2\epsilon_{S23}^f}\right)^2 - \frac{\epsilon_{22}\epsilon_{33}}{(\epsilon_{S23}^f)^2} + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}}{\epsilon_{S12}^f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{13}}{\epsilon_{S13}^f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{23}}{\epsilon_{S23}^f}\right)^2} > 1$$

Compressive failure in the transverse (matrix) direction ($\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} < 0$)

$$F_{mc} = \sqrt{\left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_{YC}^f}{2\epsilon_{S23}^f}\right)^2 - 1 \right] \left(\frac{\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33}}{\epsilon_{YC}^f}\right) + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33}}{2\epsilon_{S23}^f}\right)^2 - \frac{\epsilon_{22}\epsilon_{33}}{(\epsilon_{S23}^f)^2} + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}}{\epsilon_{S12}^f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{13}}{\epsilon_{S13}^f}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{23}}{\epsilon_{S23}^f}\right)^2} > 1$$

Exponential progressive damage evolution

Damage variables d_{ft} , d_{fc} , d_{mt} , d_{mc}

$$d_{ft} = 1 - \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{X_T \epsilon_{XT}^f L_C (F_{ft} - 1)}{G_{ft}}\right)}{F_{ft}} \quad d_{fc} = 1 - \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{X_C \epsilon_{XC}^f L_C (F_{fc} - 1)}{G_{fc}}\right)}{F_{fc}}$$

$$d_{mt} = 1 - \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{Y_T \epsilon_{YT}^f L_C (F_{mt} - 1)}{G_{mt}}\right)}{F_{mt}} \quad d_{mc} = 1 - \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{Y_C \epsilon_{YC}^f L_C (F_{mc} - 1)}{G_{mc}}\right)}{F_{mc}}$$

Synthetic damage variables D_f , D_m

$$D_f = \begin{cases} d_{ft} & \epsilon_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_{fc} & \epsilon_{11} < 0 \end{cases} \quad D_m = \begin{cases} d_{mt} & \epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} \geq 0 \\ d_{mc} & \epsilon_{22} + \epsilon_{33} < 0 \end{cases}$$

Viscous regularization

Duvaut-Lions viscosity model

$$D^v|_{t_0+\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta t}{\eta+\Delta t} D|_{t_0+\Delta t} + \frac{\eta}{\eta+\Delta t} D^v|_{t_0}$$

$$\frac{\partial D^v}{\partial D} = \frac{\Delta t}{\eta+\Delta t}$$

4. Results and discussion

Woven composites with different yarn angles

30° and 37.5°: **Nearly linear**

45°, 52.5° and 60°: **Non-linear, large deformation**

A transition of brittle to ductile characteristics

The experimental **elastic moduli**, **ultimate strengths** and **failure strains** validate the RVE model.

4. Results and discussion

▶ Large deformation process of the 52.5° coupon

▶ Post-test coupon morphologies

4. Results and discussion

Damage contours of the constituents within 30° RVE

Carbon fiber

Damage initiation

Damage evolution

Brittle failure

Coupon morphology

PC pocket

Plastic deformation

No matrix cracking

Fiber fracture-dominated failure

4. Results and discussion

Damage contours of the constituents within 52.5° RVE

Coupon morphology

Carbon fiber within yarn

Ductile failure

PC within yarn

Fiber fracture and matrix cracking co-dominated failure mode

PC pocket

Massive matrix cracking

4. Results and discussion

Shear strains of the 52.5° coupon from DIC

Yarn rotation of large yarn angle RVEs

5. Conclusions

- A transition from brittle-like to ductile load response is found as the yarn angle increases.
- A mesoscale RVE model is developed to examine this transition as well as the progressive failure of woven thermoplastic composites.
- Large deformation with yarn rotation and fabric inter-locking effects are captured in large yarn angle RVEs.
- The failure mode changes from being dominated by fiber fracture in small yarn angle RVEs to being jointly dominated by fiber and matrix damage in large yarn angle RVEs.

Thank you for your attention !

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